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The Transfer of Waste to Landfill in the Italian Regions

On average it decreased by 57% between 2004 and 2021

Istat calculates the value of waste disposal in landfills in the Italian regions. The transfer of waste to landfill is defined as the percentage of municipal waste sent to landfill out of the total municipal waste produced. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2004 and 2021.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of waste disposal in landfill in the Italian regions in 2021. Molise is in first place in terms of value of waste disposal in landfill with a value of 90.4 units, followed by Sicily with a value of 51.5 and from the Marche with a value of 50.1 units. In the middle of the table are Puglia with a value of 28.1 units, followed by Sardinia with a value of 27.9 units, and Calabria with a value of 27.6 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with a value of 5.2 units, followed by Lombardy with a value of 3.6 units and Campania with a value of 0.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in the transfer of waste to landfill in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2021. Molise is in first place for percentage change in the transfer of waste to landfill between 2004 and 2021 with a value equal to + 18.32% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 76.4 units up to a value of 90.4 units. Tuscany follows with a variation corresponding to an amount of -21.60% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 44.9 units up to a value of 35.2 units. The Marche region is in third place with a variation corresponding to an amount of -34.68% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 76.7 units up to a value of 50.1 units. In last places is Lazio with a value equal to -84.62% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 89.1 units up to a value of 13.7 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia follows with a reduction corresponding to a value of -90.17% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 52.9 units up to a value of 5.2 units. In last place Campania with a corresponding variation equal to an amount of -100.00%. On average, the value of waste disposal in landfill decreased by 57.003% between 2004 and 2021 in the Italian regions, i.e. from an amount of 65.4 units to a value of 28.1 units.

The transfer of waste to landfill in the Italian macro-regions. The transfer of waste to landfill has decreased in all Italian macro-regions and in particular by -49.05% in the Islands, by -60.81% in the Centre, by -67.40% in the South, -73.21 % in the North West, -73.40% in the North, -73.84% in the North-East, -77.59% in the South.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present the clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Three clusters are identified as follows:

- Cluster 1: Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Trentino Alto Adige, Lombardy, Emilia Romagna, Piedmont, Campania;

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- Cluster 2: Marche, Valle d'Aosta, Basilicata, Umbria, Liguria, Lazio, Calabria, Puglia, Abruzzo, Sardinia, Tuscany;
- Cluster 3: Molise, Sicily.

From an ordering point of view we can verify the following structure: $C3 > C2 > C1$. That is, the regions that send the most waste to landfill are Molise and Sicily. The second cluster is made up of southern regions with the addition of Valle d'Aosta, Liguria, Lazio and Tuscany. The third cluster is made up of the Central-Northern regions with the addition of Campania. We can therefore note that the southern regions tend to have a higher value of waste sent to landfill. The only region that has reduced levels of waste disposal in landfill is Campania. In 2021, Campania sent a value of 0 waste to landfill. However, in a general sense, it is possible to identify a contrast between Central-Southern regions and Northern regions. That is, the southern regions tend to have a much higher value of waste disposal in landfill than the northern regions even if the historical series trend shows a reduction in the variable analyzed in all Italian regions and macro-regions.

Conclusions. The transfer of waste to landfill decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021 and in all regions with the exception of Molise. We can note the existence of a contrast between central-southern regions and northern regions. The central-southern regions tend to have higher levels of waste disposal in landfill than the northern regions, also in the general reduction in the value of the variable analyzed. A very particular case is represented by Campania. According to the data reported by Istat, the value of waste transfers to landfills in Campania reached the value of 0 in 2021. Obviously, we can note that the variable analyzed refers to official data or to waste transfers to landfills which are surveyed and controlled. The variable is not able to represent landfill disposal that occurs illegally and without authorization. It is very likely that there are illegal landfills in the Italian regions which would also be possible to estimate through an integrated analysis of the legality indices analyzed together with the attitudes towards environmental sustainability and the green and circular economy. However, the estimate of the existence of illegal landfills is absent in national statistics. It is a serious lack that could be filled through specific estimates made through the analysis of socio-economic and ethical components detected at regional and local level. It is therefore certainly a positive thing that in the Italian regions there has been a reduction in the transfer of waste to landfill. However, from the data it is not possible to reconstruct the real extent of the phenomenon due to the lack of data that estimates the presence and size of illegal waste landfills in the Italian regions.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Regioni	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
Piemonte	56,5	55,8	50,8	45,3	41,4	41,7	41,5	42,1	36,3

Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	76,7	67,9	65,5	63,9	61,7	67,2	59,1	57,2	54,8
Liguria	82	78,5	89,9	91,8	84,7	83,5	78,5	74,2	66,2
Lombardia	19,6	15,4	16,5	9,7	8,1	6,7	7,7	6,7	7,9
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	43,7	40,5	39,2	31,9	35,8	26	29,2	25,6	24,4
Veneto	36,7	36,6	35,6	29	22,1	22	19,3	13,8	10,9
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	52,9	38,7	37,3	28	16,3	14,5	14,9	12,3	7,2
Emilia-Romagna	41,2	42,8	38,2	37,6	40,2	33,6	27,7	24,9	30
Toscana	44,9	46,1	50,2	50,6	50,7	47,7	43,4	42,5	42,5
Umbria	54,5	57	59,5	57	60,3	55,2	66,8	62,2	59,8
Marche	76,7	65,3	65,6	62,5	62,8	65,4	62,9	61,1	56,8
Lazio	89,1	82,3	85,1	83,1	85,8	80,5	73,9	71,1	65,2
Abruzzo	77,4	74,8	80,7	79,2	79,7	60,5	59	37,5	18,8
Molise	76,4	95,4	92,5	98,2	90,3	87,8	83,9	91,2	104,9
Campania	70,1	62,9	59,2	73	75,5	62,3	48,5	24,4	12,5
Puglia	91,6	93,2	89,9	91,1	79,8	73,5	66,9	58,7	62,6
Basilicata	75,1	61,4	59,5	72,6	79,9	79,2	83,4	79,5	54,8
Calabria	74,7	84,6	67,6	54,7	56,9	65,3	60,9	74,5	81,8
Sicilia	95,4	91	93,7	92,5	88,9	91,1	93,4	90,7	83,4
Sardegna	72,1	73,6	65,3	58,1	52,1	42	40,6	44,6	38,3
Regioni	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Piemonte	35,6	28,7	26,3	24,8	22	15	12	12,6	12,2
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	54,6	61,8	55,9	47,9	43,4	42,1	39,5	38,2	38,2
Liguria	63,9	43,2	12,3	17	25,3	31	36,9	36,2	39,6
Lombardia	5,8	7,1	5,3	4,2	4,9	4,3	4,2	3,5	3,6
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	18,9	16,9	14,3	12,8	9,8	8,6	11,5	12,3	10,1
Veneto	9,2	12,4	11,1	9,8	12,8	13,5	14,4	14,7	16,1
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	6,8	6,1	8,5	3,5	6,3	6,8	7,8	11,4	5,2
Emilia-Romagna	30,8	30,7	22,5	16,3	14,1	10,7	9,4	9,2	7,5
Toscana	37,3	37,3	32,5	30,8	32,2	32,5	33,8	36,4	35,2
Umbria	54,8	56,2	52,6	57,1	39,4	39,7	41,1	37	33,6
Marche	51,9	50,8	58,1	49,1	36,5	38,4	42,8	48,1	50,1
Lazio	45,8	20,4	13,3	13,4	11,3	12	20,6	15,7	13,7
Abruzzo	15,5	13,2	21,4	33,2	41,3	37,6	34,4	29,2	27,5
Molise	113,4	111	104,1	90,2	92,8	101,7	90	79,3	90,4
Campania	19,4	8,6	4,9	3,9	3,3	2,8	1,3	1,6	0
Puglia	66,6	75,1	51,9	47,9	42,8	37,1	36	33,7	28,1
Basilicata	57,1	52	25,2	29,9	36,2	24,8	26	19	44
Calabria	71,2	47,3	59,8	58,2	55,3	52,4	40,3	27,4	27,6
Sicilia	93,5	84,4	82,8	79,9	72,9	69	58,5	58,9	51,5
Sardegna	34,8	33,5	27,6	31,8	35,6	25,4	22,4	23,4	27,9

	Nord	Nord- ovest	Nord-est	Centro	Mezzogiorno	Sud	Isole	Italia
2004	39,1	37,7	40,9	69,4	81,9	78,1	89,5	59,8
2005	37	34,7	39,9	65,6	80	76,6	86,6	57,4
2006	36	35,1	37,2	68,7	77,3	72,4	86,8	56,8
2007	31,2	29,8	33	67,4	79,5	77,1	84,2	55,1
2008	28,5	26,7	30,9	68,9	76,8	75,2	80	53
2009	26,4	26	26,9	65,6	71,1	67,1	79,2	49,5
2010	24,8	25,9	23,5	61,6	66	58,7	80,7	46,3
2011	22,6	24,8	19,8	59,6	57,7	46,4	79,9	42,1
2012	21,8	22,9	20,5	56,2	51,8	41,3	72,7	39,1
2013	20,5	21	19,7	44,2	55,6	43,6	79,7	36,9
2014	19	17,6	20,7	32,4	49,4	38	72,3	31,5
2015	14,1	12,2	16,4	28,2	43,7	30,6	69,9	26,5
2016	11,9	11,5	12,4	26,9	42,4	29,6	68,4	24,7
2017	12,3	12,1	12,6	23,7	40,2	28,4	64	23,4
2018	10,8	10,4	11,2	24,3	36,3	25,5	58,2	21,5
2019	10,6	10,1	11,3	29,3	31,2	22,4	49,5	20,9
2020	10,6	9,7	11,7	28,4	29,2	19,2	50,1	20,1
2021	10,4	10,1	10,7	27,2	26,7	17,5	45,6	19